

REPORT

A.2.2.7: Validation of the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for H₂, CO, N₂ and O₂

As part of WP2 task 2.2, BiometCAP partners have demonstrated the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in Task 2.1 (specifically in A2.1.4) using the following validated methods: gas chromatography, spectroscopy and spectrometry analytical systems. The validation exercise is shown on the map below:

TUBITAK, NPL and CMI will each validate the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for hydrogen, carbon monoxide, oxygen and nitrogen using a gas chromatography thermal conductivity detector (GC-TCD). TUBITAK and CMI will use the static standard produced in A1.1.5 and NPL will use the dynamic system from A1.2.1. A short written report will be produced by TUBITAK, with input from NPL and CMI.

The three reports are gathered in this document.

REPORT

A.2.2.7: Validation Report for GC-TCD Analysis of Hydrogen, Carbon Monoxide and Nitrogen in Biomethane

Task 2.2.7

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1. Introduction

The measurement of biomethane emissions has some challenges in terms of gas composition, equipment requirements, and sampling. As a result, a practical and accurate measuring system is required. Biomethane can be measured with different techniques such as GC-TCD, GC-FID, NDIR, and FTIR. Method validation studies are carried out to contribute to metrological infrastructure.

In this work, the validation parameters including selectivity, limit of detection, limit of quantification, working range and linearity, trueness and precision were assessed. Utilizing these data, each component's measurement uncertainty was estimated.

This report describes the method validation study for GC-TCD analyses of hydrogen, carbon monoxide and nitrogen in biomethane gas mixtures prepared within BiometCAP project.

2. Planning of Validation

The general procedure for determining the performance characteristics of the instrument is summarised in Table 1. Detailed process descriptions are provided in the following sections.

Table 1. Method validation planning

Step	Phase	Description	Document section reference
1	Planning	Specify the components required to be measured by the instrument and the measurement range for each over which the instrument shall be evaluated.	Section 3.2
2	Planning	Establish the functional descriptions of the response functions assumed by the instrument for each specified component.	Section 3.3
3	Planning	Establish the composition and uncertainty of the calibration gas mixture(s) for performance tests	Section 3.4
4	Planning	Specify a set of reference gas mixtures (calibration gases) with compositions covering all ranges for all components specified in step 1.	Section 3.5
5	Experimental	Perform a multi-point calibration experiment by collecting instrument response data for measurements of the reference gas mixtures specified in step 4. The entire experiment should be conducted within a time period equivalent to that between routine calibrations.	Section 4
6	Calculation	Calculating the uncertainty budget	Section 5

3. Performance Evaluation Procedure

3.1. General requirements

The extent of the performance characteristic validation is summarised in Table 2. Limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ), linearity (working range), trueness (bias) and precision parameters are evaluated in method validation.

Table 2. Extent of validation

Performance characteristic	Analytical application		
	Component identification	Component detection	Component quantification
Selectivity	x		x
Limit of detection		x	
Limit of quantification	x		x
Working range	x		x
Trueness	x		x
Precision	x		x

3.2. Step 1 (planning): Specification of components and ranges

The components studied are carbon monoxide, nitrogen and hydrogen. The measurement ranges for these components are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Components and ranges

Component	Upper limit value	Reference	Calibration range
Hydrogen	2 cmol mol ⁻¹	EN 16723-2:2017	(0.5 -10) cmol mol ⁻¹
Nitrogen	5 cmol mol ⁻¹	EN 16723-2:2017	(0.1 – 25) cmol mol ⁻¹
Carbon monoxide	1000 μmol mol ⁻¹	EN 16723-1:2016	(500 – 2000) μmol mol ⁻¹

3.3. Step 2 (planning): Response function specification

The instrument system has been assumed to be linear. Depending on the availability of the reference gases, three or five point calibrations are planned for CO, H₂ and N₂.

3.4. Step 3 (planning): Calibration gas composition specification

Validation tests will be carried out using two separate gas mixtures prepared in activity A1.1.5. The details of these mixtures are given in Table 4. Mixture preparation is carried out according to ISO 6142-1 [1] and verified against internal gas standards using GC-TCD. The uncertainty values (k=1) given in Table 4 are those for gravimetric preparation.

Table 4. Concentrations of the gas mixtures prepared for method validation study

Component	Unit	Composition (Mixture 1)	Composition (Mixture 2)
		(Cylinder: PSM206700)	(Cylinder: PSM206696)
Hydrogen	cmol/mol	1.954 ± 0.001	9.974 ± 0.003
Nitrogen	cmol/mol	2.044 ± 0.001	10.051 ± 0.001
Carbon monoxide	μmol/mol	979.3 ± 0.6	997.9 ± 0.6
Methane	-	Balance	Balance

3.5. Step 4 (planning): Reference gas suite specification

Calibration of the instrument is carried out using TUBITAK UME's reference gas mixtures. The gas mixtures with the compositions given in Table 5 are used as reference gas mixtures during method validation study for N₂ and H₂ components.

Table 5. Amount of fractions of the reference gas mixtures of N₂ and H₂

Cylinder No	Amount of Fraction (cmol/mol)	
	N ₂	H ₂
UME499821	0.122	-
UME499775	0.649	0.973
UME298291	14.917	0.502
UME499803	17.918	4.054
UME499802	20.421	7.444
UME499796	24.962	9.985

A binary mixture (CO in methane) is used for method validation study of CO. It is diluted to 3 different concentrations according to ISO 6145-7 [2]. The amount fraction of CO in the reference gas mixture and the target CO calibration points are given in Table 6.

Table 6. Amount of fractions of the gas mixtures obtained for method validation study of CO

Cylinder No	Amount of Fraction (cmol/mol)	Diluted to (µmol/mol)
PSM206723	2.997 ± 0.001	500
		1000
		2000

4. Performance Evaluation

The details of the measurement method and the evaluation of the performance characteristics given in Table 2 are given in the following sections.

4.1. Details of the measurement method

Performance evaluation tests were carried out using Gas Chromatography (GC)-Thermal Conductivity Detector (TCD). The instrument used is Agilent 7890B gas chromatography equipped with two TCDs, split/splitless injector, gas injection valve, including GC ChemStation software (Rev. B. 04.03-SP2 [108]).

Each cylinder is injected 10 times and used for determination of average values and uncertainties of the measurements. The pressure of the sample gas fed to instrument is controlled by an electronic pressure controller at a set of 150 mbar.

GC-TCD parameters are given below:

Oven

Equilibration Time :1 min
Max Temperature :220 degrees C
Slow Fan :Disabled
Oven Program :On
60 °C for 1 min
#1 then 20 °C/min to 80 °C for 0 min
#2 then 30 °C/min to 190 °C for 0.33 min
Run Time :5.9967 min

Front SS Inlet He

Mode :Split
Heater :On 250 °C
Pressure :On 18 psi
Total Flow :On 86.452 mL/min
Septum Purge Flow :On 3 mL/min
Split Ratio :20 :1
Split Flow :79.479 mL/min

Column #1

Agilent G3591-81141 2 ft Unibeads IS 60-80 mesh
200 °C: Packed
In: PCM B-2 He
Out: Back Detector TCD

Pressure Program On
9.8 psi for 0 min
Run Time 5.9967 min

Column #2+#3

Agilent g3591-81142 4 ft Unibeads IS + Agilent g63591-81022 8 ft Molesieve 5A 60/80 mesh
200 °C: Packed
In: PCM B-1 He
Out: Other

Const Col + Makeup :Off

Back Detector TCD

Heater :On 250 °C
 Reference Flow :On 45 mL/min
 Makeup Flow :On 2 mL/min
 Const Col + Makeup :Off
 Negative Polarity :Off

Aux Detector TCD

Heater :On 250 °C
 Reference Flow :On 45 mL/min
 Makeup Flow :On 2 mL/min
 Const Col + Makeup :Off
 Negative Polarity :On

4.2. *Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantification*

Reference gas mixtures and working standards were used to determine the LOD and LOQ which can be defined as the lowest possible concentration of an analyte at which the method can detect and quantify, respectively. Either static or dynamic working standards were measured and verified against reference gas mixtures according to single-point calibration method (ISO 12963 [3]).

The standard deviation was used to calculate LOD and LOQ utilizing the following formulas:

$$s'_0 = \frac{s_0}{\sqrt{n}}$$

$$\text{LOD} = 3 \times s'_0$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times s'_0$$

CO

Due to lack of low concentration reference gas mixture of CO with methane as matrix gas, the study was performed using CO in N₂ gas mixtures. The reference gas mixture UME266300 (100 μmol/mol CO in N₂) and working standard PSM266332 (100 μmol/mol CO in N₂) were analyzed to assess the LOD and LOQ levels of the instrument for the CO component. The following are the LOD and LOQ results for the CO evaluated on two different days using GC-TCD (Table 7).

Table 7. LOD and LOQ results for the CO component obtained with GC-TCD

Injection number	Day 1, (μmol/mol) (08.05.2024)	Day 2, (μmol/mol) (09.05.2024)
1	102.3	101.0
2	99.8	102.9
3	103.0	100.7
4	100.5	98.6

5	99.1	101.0
6	101.3	100.7
7	103.6	100.3
8	101.0	103.4
9	100.3	100.0
10	99.7	97.9
Standard Deviation, s'_0	1.5	1.7
LOD, $3 \times s'_0$	4.5	5.0
LOQ, $10 \times s'_0$	15.0	16.8

The average LOD and LOQ results for CO component are given in Table 8.

Table 8. Average LOD and LOQ results for CO component

Parameter	Concentration ($\mu\text{mol/mol}$)
LOD	4.8
LOQ	15.9

N₂

The reference gas mixture UME499775 (see Table 5) was diluted to 66.1 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ using pure CH₄ according to ISO 6145-7 [2] using MFCs. The working standard PSM499800 (598.1 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ N₂ in CH₄) was also diluted to 67.4 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ using pure CH₄. The LOD and LOQ results for the N₂ component obtained on two different days are presented in Table 9.

Table 9. LOD and LOQ results for the N₂ component obtained with GC-TCD

Injection number	Day 1, ($\mu\text{mol/mol}$) (30.04.2024)	Day 2, ($\mu\text{mol/mol}$) (02.05.2024)
1	64.3	68.5
2	68.1	67.1
3	64.9	67.1
4	65.9	68.2
5	65.4	68.5
6	68.2	67.1
7	69.1	65.5
8	67.2	68.4
9	67.4	65.3
10	67.6	66.7
Standard Deviation, s'_0	1.6	1.5
LOD, $3 \times s'_0$	4.8	4.5
LOQ, $10 \times s'_0$	15.9	14.9

Table 10 shows the average LOD and LOQ results for the N₂ component.

Table 10. Average LOD and LOQ results for N₂ component

Parameter	Concentration (μmol/mol)
LOD	4.6
LOQ	15.4

H₂

UME499775 reference gas mixture (see Table 5) was diluted to 99.1 μmol/mol. PSM499800 used as working standard with the concentration of 894.8 μmol/mol was diluted to 100.8 μmol/mol. Pure methane was used as dilution gas. Measurements were performed on two different days. The results are presented in Table 11.

Table 11. LOD and LOQ results for the H₂ component obtained with GC-TCD

Injection number	Day 1, (μmol/mol) (30.04.2024)	Day 2, (μmol/mol) (02.05.2024)
1	100.2	105.5
2	106.5	103.5
3	107.3	99.7
4	102.7	102.8
5	104.4	104.7
6	99.8	104.5
7	100.9	109.3
8	104.4	106.5
9	102.7	103.7
10	98.2	108.9
Standard Deviation, s'_0	3.0	2.9
LOD, $3 \times s'_0$	8.9	8.6
LOQ, $10 \times s'_0$	29.7	28.5

Table 12 displays the average LOD and LOQ values for the H₂ component.

Table 12. Average LOD and LOQ results for H₂ component

Parameter	Concentration (μmol/mol)
LOD	8.7
LOQ	29.1

4.3. Selectivity

The selectivity is the capability of the method to separate and quantify the response of the target component in the presence of other component. GC method provides successful separation of the components without any interference. The GC-TCD chromatograms obtained are presented in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Figure 1. The GC-TCD chromatogram of N₂ and CO components in CH₄ matrix

Figure 2. The GC-TCD chromatogram of H₂ component in CH₄ matrix

4.4. **Linearity (Working Range)**

The reference gas mixtures at concentrations that covered the concentrations of the sample cylinders (PSM206696 and PSM206700) were chosen for the working range study of CO, N₂ and H₂ components in CH₄ matrix. The model equations and correlation coefficients for each component were determined using the linearity data.

CO

For linearity assessment of CO component, binary mixture PSM206723 (2.997 cmol/mol CO in CH₄) was diluted to three concentrations given in Table 6. The analyses of diluted mixtures and two sample mixtures were carried out in three different days, i.e., 16 May 2024, 23 May 2024, and 24 May 2024.

For each day, an x-y (concentration-signal) graph was plotted in Excel using the reference values and instrument responses obtained from measurements. Correlation coefficient (R² value) was calculated. Afterwards, the y-x (signal-concentration) graph was plotted. The fitting model was selected as linear. The CO concentrations in the samples (PSM206696 and PSM206700) were determined by using the fitting equation shown on the linearity graphs in Figure 3, Figure 4 and Figure 5. Table 13 shows the responses and amount of fractions obtained from the calibration curves in three sets of measurements.

Based on these results, it can be noted that correlation coefficient is close to 1 (R² > 0.999) and that there is a linear relationship between the response for each gas mixtures measured with GC-TCD and CO concentration.

Figure 3. Linearity graph of CO obtained on 16 May 2024.

Figure 4. Linearity graph of CO obtained on 23 May 2024.

Figure 5. Linearity graph of CO obtained on 24 May 2024.

Table 13. The amount of fractions of the samples for CO obtained with the calibration curves

Cylinder	Analysis Set	x_grav (µmol/mol)	y (Area)	x_fit (µmol/mol)	x_fit_average (µmol/mol)
PSM206700	1	979.3	45.55	996.2	999.2

	2		45.10	999.3	
	3		45.13	1002.1	
PSM206696	1	997.9	46.75	1021.1	1023.3
	2		46.19	1022.2	
	3		46.30	1026.5	

N₂

For linearity assessment of N₂ component, reference gas mixtures with the cylinder numbers of UME499821, UME298291, UME499803, UME499802 and UME499796 were used. The analyses of reference gas mixtures and two sample mixtures were carried out in three different days, i.e., 22 February 2024, 18 April 2024, and 24 April 2024.

For each day, an x-y (concentration-signal) graph was plotted in Excel using the reference values and instrument responses obtained from measurements. Correlation coefficient (R² value) was calculated. Afterwards, the y-x (signal-concentration) graph was plotted. The fitting model was selected as linear. The N₂ concentrations in the samples (PSM206696 and PSM206700) were determined by using the fitting equation shown on the linearity graphs in Figure 6, Figure 7 and Figure 8.

Table 14 shows the responses and amount of fractions obtained from the calibration curves in three sets of measurements.

Based on these results, it can be noted that correlation coefficient is close to 1 (R² > 0.999) and that there is a linear relationship between the response for each gas mixtures measured with GC-TCD and N₂ concentration.

Figure 6. Linearity graph of N₂ obtained on 22 February 2024.

Figure 7. Linearity graph of N₂ obtained on 18 April 2024.

Figure 8. Linearity graph of N₂ obtained on 24 April 2024.

Table 14. The amount of fractions of the samples for obtained with the calibration curves

Cylinder	Analysis Set	x_grav (μmol/mol)	y (Area)	x_fit (μmol/mol)	x_fit_average (μmol/mol)
PSM206700	1	2.044	970.84	2.128	2.038
	2		942.57	1.996	
	3		935.41	1.992	
PSM206696	1	10.051	4713.33	10.090	10.088
	2		4579.96	10.095	
	3		4583.98	10.080	

H₂

For linearity assessment of H₂ component, reference gas mixtures with the cylinder numbers of UME499796, UME499802, UME298291, UME499775 and UME499803 were used. The analyses of reference gas mixtures and two sample mixtures were carried out in three different days, i.e., 22 February 2024, 18 April 2024, and 24 April 2024.

For each day, an x-y (concentration-signal) graph was plotted in Excel using the reference values and instrument responses obtained from measurements. Correlation coefficient (R² value) was calculated. Afterwards, the y-x (signal-concentration) graph was plotted. The fitting model was selected as linear. The H₂ concentrations in the samples (PSM206696 and PSM206700) were determined by using the fitting equation shown on the linearity graphs in Figure 9, Figure 10 and Figure 11. Table 15 shows the responses and amount of fractions obtained from the calibration curves in three sets of measurements.

Based on these results, it can be noted that correlation coefficient is close to 1 (R² > 0.999) and that there is a linear relationship between the response for each gas mixtures measured with GC-TCD and H₂ concentration.

Figure 9. Linearity graph of H₂ obtained on 22 February 2024.

Figure 10. Linearity graph of H₂ obtained on 18 April 2024.

Figure 11. Linearity graph of H₂ obtained on 24 April 2024.

Table 15. The amount of fractions of the samples for H₂ obtained with the calibration curves

Cylinder	Analysis Set	x_grav (cmol/mol)	y (Area)	x_fit (cmol/mol)	x_fit_average (cmol/mol)
PSM206700	1	1.954	343.45	1.947	1.947
	2		335.27	1.952	
	3		333.46	1.943	
PSM206696	1	9.974	1773.80	9.959	9.967
	2		1728.80	9.981	
	3		1728.23	9.962	

4.5. Trueness (Bias)

Evaluation of trueness was performed for CO, N₂ and H₂ components using Approach 1 given in Protocol [4] (Assessment against a reference material). Analyses were carried out on 3 different days. The reference gas at the proper concentration was employed.

Recovery:

The formula utilized in the recovery calculation is as follows:

$$R (\%) = \frac{\bar{x}}{x_{ref}} \times 100$$

- \bar{x} : measured value
- x_{ref} : reference value
- R (%) : apparent recovery

Recovery results of CO, N₂ and H₂ components in biomethane samples are presented in Table 16.

Table 16. Recovery results of CO, N₂ and H₂ components.

Cylinder	Component	Certificate Value	Measured Value	Recovery* (%)
PSM206696	CO, μmol/mol	997.9	1023.3	102.54
	N ₂ , cmol/mol	10.051	10.088	100.37
	H ₂ , cmol/mol	9.974	9.967	99.94
PSM206700	CO, μmol/mol	979.3	999.2	102.03
	N ₂ , cmol/mol	2.044	2.038	99.73
	H ₂ , cmol/mol	1.954	1.947	99.65

*Calculated from the average of three measurements

Uncertainty from bias

Uncertainty from bias was calculated according to the equation given below.

$$u_{bias} = \sqrt{u_{\bar{x}}^2 + u_{x_{ref}}^2}$$

$u_{\bar{x}}$: standard uncertainty of measured value

$u_{x_{ref}}$: standard uncertainty of reference value

where $u_{\bar{x}}$ was determined by substituting the relevant data into equation given below:

$$u_{\bar{x}} = \frac{s}{\sqrt{n}}$$

s : standard deviation of the measurements

n : number of measurements

Calculations were performed for the measurement results for one reference gas mixture of each component. Bias uncertainty of CO, N₂ and H₂ components in biomethane samples are summarized in Table 17.

Table 17. Results of uncertainty from bias of CO, N₂ and H₂ components.

Mixture	Component, reference value	$u_{x_{ref}}$	$u_{\bar{x}}$	u_{bias}
PSM206723 (diluted)	CO, 1000 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$	2.44	0.43	2.48
UME499821	N ₂ , 0.122 cmol/mol	0.00050	0.00041	0.00065
UME298291	H ₂ , 0.502 cmol/mol	0.00083	0.00018	0.00085

4.6. Precision

Precision was evaluated using ANOVA (one way), taking into consideration replicates within days (10 injections) as well as replicates between days (3 sets). The calculations were performed using measurement results for both samples (PSM206696 and PSM206700) on three different days.

ANOVA results for all components are given in Table 18 to Table 23.

Table 18. CO component in PSM206696

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	11.5996	9	1.288846	0.121406207	0.998647	2.392814
Within Groups	212.3197	20	10.61598			
Total	223.9193	29				

Overall average 1023.323

s(wd) 3.258

s(wd) [%] 0.318

s(wb) 95% Cf.Lim. [%] 0.360

s(bd) MSB<MSW

s(bd) [%] MSB<MSW %

u*(bd) 1.058 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$

u*(bd) [%] 0.10 %

u(bd) [%] 0.10 %

bd: between days

wd: within days

Table 19. CO component in PSM206700

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	3.0537	9	0.339302	0.035061306	0.999992	2.392814
Within Groups	193.5479	20	9.677393			
Total	196.6016	29				
Overall average	999.060					
s(wd)	3.111					
s(wd) [%]	0.311					
s(wb) 95% Cf.Lim. [%]	0.352					
s(bd)	MSB<MSW					
s(bd) [%]	MSB<MSW	%				
u*(bd)	1.010	μmol/mol				
u*(bd) [%]	0.10	%				
u(bd) [%]	0.10	%				

bd: between days
wd: within days

Table 20. N₂ component in PSM206696

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.0003	9	3.61E-05	0.032308089	0.999994	2.392814
Within Groups	0.0223	20	0.001116			
Total	0.0226	29				
Overall average	10.096					
s(wd)	0.033					
s(wd) [%]	0.331					
s(wb) 95% Cf.Lim. [%]	0.374					
s(bd)	MSB<MSW					
s(bd) [%]	MSB<MSW	%				
u*(bd)	0.011	cmol/mol				
u*(bd) [%]	0.11	%				

u(bd) [%] **0.11** %

bd: between days
wd: within days

Table 21. N₂ component in PSM206700

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.0002	9	2.41E-05	0.024756562	0.999998	2.392814
Within Groups	0.0195	20	0.000974			
Total	0.0197	29				

Overall average 2.053
s(wd) 0.031
s(wd) [%] 1.520
s(wd) 95% Cf.Lim. [%] 1.720

s(bd) **MSB<MSW**
s(bd) [%] **MSB<MSW** %
u*(bd) **0.010** **cmol/mol**
u*(bd) [%] **0.49** %

u(bd) [%] **0.49** %

bd: between days
wd: within days

Table 22. H₂ component in PSM206696

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.0009	9	9.6E-05	0.446360756	0.893013	2.392814
Within Groups	0.0043	20	0.000215			
Total	0.0052	29				

Overall average 9.967
s(wd) 0.015
s(wd) [%] 0.147
s(wb) 95% Cf.Lim. [%] 0.166

s(bd) **MSB<MSW**
s(bd) [%] **MSB<MSW** %

u*(bd)	0.005	cmol/mol
u*(bd) [%]	0.05	%

u(bd) [%]	0.05	%
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bd: between days

wd: within days

Table 23. H₂ component in PSM206700

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.00001	9	7.57E-07	0.032473727	0.999994	2.392814
Within Groups	0.0005	20	2.33E-05			
Total	0.0005	29				

Overall average 1.947

s(wd) 0.005

s(wd) [%] 0.248

s(wb) 95% Cf.Lim. [%] 0.281

s(bd)	MSB<MSW
s(bd) [%]	MSB<MSW %
u*(bd)	0.002 cmol/mol
u*(bd) [%]	0.08 %

u(bd) [%]	0.08	%
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bd: between days

wd: within days

The above given ANOVA results for each component are summarized in Table 24.

Table 24. ANOVA results of the samples (%)

Component	Cylinder No	
	PSM206696	PSM206700
CO	0.10	0.10
N ₂	0.11	0.49
H ₂	0.05	0.08

5. Uncertainty Evaluation

The basis for the uncertainty budget is formed by the uncertainty evaluation from the validation parameters including precision and bias from measurements using reference gas mixture. The measurement uncertainty of samples obtained from the CurveFit software determined according to ISO 6143 [5] has been added as the last uncertainty source to cover the uncertainty of the reference gas mixtures.

The combined standard uncertainty was determined by the following equation:

$$u_c = \sqrt{u_{prec}^2 + u_{bias}^2 + u_m^2}$$

where

u_{prec} : standard uncertainty from precision (from ANOVA results)

u_{bias} : standard uncertainty from bias

u_m : standard uncertainty of measured value from ISO 6143

The expanded uncertainty was determined by multiplying the combined standard uncertainty by a coverage factor of 2 with a confidence interval of 95%.

Uncertainty budgets of CO, N₂ and H₂ components in biomethane sample (PSM206700) are presented in Table 25, Table 26 and Table 27, respectively.

Table 25. Uncertainty budget of CO in biomethane

Uncertainty Sources	PSM206700 (997.9 μmol/mol)	PSM206696 (979.3 μmol/mol)
u_{prec} , (μmol/mol)	1.010	1.058
u_{bias} , (μmol/mol)	2.475	2.475
u_m , (μmol/mol)	1.577	1.584
Combined measurement uncertainty, (μmol/mol)	3.104	3.123
Expanded measurement uncertainty, (μmol/mol)	6.208	6.246
Relative expanded measurement uncertainty, (k=2), %	0.63	0.63

Table 26. Uncertainty budget of N₂ in biomethane

Uncertainty Sources	PSM206700	PSM206696
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	(2.044 cmol/mol)	(10.051 cmol/mol)
u_{prec} , (μmol/mol)	0.0101	0.0108
u_{bias} , (μmol/mol)	0.0006	0.0006
u_m , (μmol/mol)	0.0051	0.0139
Combined measurement uncertainty, (μmol/mol)	0.011	0.018
Expanded measurement uncertainty, (μmol/mol)	0.023	0.035
Relative expanded measurement uncertainty, (k=2), %	1.11*	0.35

* This high uncertainty value is due to uncertainty source from precision. The N₂ measurement results in Set 1 differs from those of Set 2 and Set 3 which yielded high uncertainty in ANOVA analysis.

Table 27. Uncertainty budget of H₂ in biomethane

Uncertainty Sources	PSM206700 (1.954 cmol/mol)	PSM206696 (9.974 cmol/mol)
u_{prec} , (μmol/mol)	0.0016	0.0048
u_{bias} , (μmol/mol)	0.0008	0.0008
u_m , (μmol/mol)	0.0029	0.0159
Combined measurement uncertainty, (μmol/mol)	0.003	0.017
Expanded measurement uncertainty, (μmol/mol)	0.007	0.033
Relative expanded measurement uncertainty, (k=2), %	0.35	0.33

6. References

- [1] International Organization for Standardization, ISO 6142-1:2015 “Gas analysis - Preparation of calibration gas mixtures - Part 1: Gravimetric method for Class I mixtures”
- [2] International Organization for Standardization, ISO 6145-7:2018 “Gas analysis - Preparation of calibration gas mixtures using dynamic methods, Part 7: Thermal mass-flow controllers”.
- [3] International Organization for Standardization, ISO 12963:2017+A1:2020 “Gas analysis — Comparison methods for the determination of the composition of gas mixtures based on one- and two-point calibration”.
- [4] Activity Report, “A2.1.14: Protocol for the performance evaluation of gas analysers used for biomethane conformity assessment”, BiometCAP Project, ver1.0, 2024.
- [5] International Organization for Standardization, ISO 6143:2001 “Gas analysis - Comparison methods for determining and checking the composition of calibration gas mixtures”

REPORT

A2.2.7: Validation of the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for hydrogen, carbon monoxide, oxygen and nitrogen using GC-TCD with the static standards produced in A1.1.5.

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1. Introduction

The EURAMET project, “BiometCAP” has developed a performance assessment protocol for evaluating instruments and methods used for biomethane conformity assessment. In this report, the analytical methods used to determine the concentrations of hydrogen (H₂), carbon monoxide (CO), oxygen (O₂) and nitrogen (N₂) in methane matrix using gas chromatography thermal conductivity detector (GC-TCD) were validated in accordance with the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4.

The methods were validated using dynamic standards generated by the thermal mass flow controller (MFC) based dynamic dilution system developed by NPL in A1.2.1. The blend ratios to achieve the desired amount fractions were calculated, and the dynamic standards were generated by using the MFC dynamic dilution system to dilute the static standard produced in A1.1.5 (D133074) with N6.0 purity grade methane gas. The MFC dynamic dilution system was validated using a check standard (D133080). The static standards were prepared gravimetrically and validated against NPL primary reference materials (NPL PRMs).

The parameters that were evaluated as part of this report include:

- Linearity
- Trueness
- Precision
- Limit of detection and limit of quantification
- Interferences

The general procedure for determining the performance characteristics of the instrument, taken from the protocol developed in A2.1.4 are summarised in Table 28.

Table 28: Procedure to evaluate performance characteristics of instrument.

Step	Phase	Description	Plan
1	Planning	Specify the components required to be measured by the instrument and the measurement range for each over which the instrument shall be evaluated.	Hydrogen, carbon monoxide, oxygen and nitrogen are measured at the ranges specified in Table 29.
2	Planning	Establish the functional descriptions of the response functions assumed by the instrument for each specified component.	The GC-TCD response should be linear, with a minimum R ² value of 0.995.
3	Planning	Specify a set of reference gas mixtures (calibration gases) with compositions covering all ranges for all components specified in step 1.	D133074 is diluted to cover all ranges of interest for all components specified in step 1. D133080 is used as a static check standard.
4	Planning	Establish the composition and uncertainty of the calibration gas mixture(s) to be used for routine calibration of the instrument.	Gravimetric composition and uncertainties are calculated using NPL software GravCalc2.

5	Experimental	Perform a multi-point calibration experiment by collecting instrument response data for measurements of the reference gas mixtures specified in step 4. The entire experiment should be conducted within a time period equivalent to that between routine calibrations.	D133074 is diluted with N6.0 methane gas using MFC dynamic dilution system, and calibration curves are produced for each component. The curves are validated against the check standard which was produced from A1.1.5 for trueness, linearity, and selectivity. The measurements are repeated for 4 days over 3 weeks to assess precision.
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2. Analytical method

H₂, CO, O₂ and N₂ are identified and analysed using the TCD. The TCD operates by measuring the thermal conductivity of the gases flowing through it. It contains a heated filament in a flow cell, where the carrier gas establishes a baseline. When the static standard flows through it, the gases that have different thermal conductivity to the carrier gas changes the heat dissipation from the filament, causing a shift in temperature and electrical resistance. The resistance change alters the voltage, which generates a signal proportional to the concentration of the gases in the static standard.

The analysis method used a GC that has two TCD channels with helium and argon as the carrier gases. The first TCD utilises a Hayesep Q column measuring 2m x 2.0mm ID x 1/8" OD, followed by a MolSieve 5A measuring 9 ft x 2mm ID x 1/8" OD. The second TCD utilises a HP-PLOT Q PT column measuring 15m x 0.5mm x 40µm followed by columns HP-PLOT MolSieve measuring 30m x 0.53mm x 50 µm and FS Tubing measuring 0.25mm x 1.5m. The oven temperature was set to 35°C. The runtime of the method is 12 minutes, which allows complete separation of H₂, CO, O₂ and N₂ from methane.

The dynamic gas standards were generated using the MFC dynamic dilution system. The system was connected to the GC-TCD via a SilcoNert® 2000 coated stainless steel tubing, as shown in Figure 12. The flow rate to the GC was set to 25 ml min⁻¹ for all measurements and a vent line used to vent the excess flow.

Figure 12: MFC dynamic dilution system developed in A1.2.1.

3. Reference standards

High accuracy, SI-traceable gas reference standards were prepared gravimetrically according to ISO 6142-1 using techniques developed at NPL. The standards were prepared in a methane matrix in passivated BOC SPECTRA-SEAL cylinders. The reference standards were validated in accordance with ISO 6143 using previously developed GC-TCD methods. The concentrations of H₂, CO, O₂ and N₂ chosen to produce the calibration curve using the MFC dynamic dilution system was based on the range of interest according to EN 16723-1, EN 16723-2 and stakeholder input, as shown in Table 29. The concentrations of the standards are reported in Table 30.

Table 29: Range of interest required for dynamic dilution of static standard.

Component	Lower range of interest ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	Higher range of interest ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)
Hydrogen	100	100000
Carbon monoxide	1000	1000
Oxygen	10	10000
Nitrogen	100	100000

Table 30: Gravimetric compositions of PRMs used in the validation.

Component	Amount fraction ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	
	D133074	D133080
Hydrogen	104060.886	20160.221
Carbon monoxide	962.805	1009.282
Oxygen	1922.799	406.6774
Nitrogen	94213.246	19973.566
Methane	Balance	Balance

4. Linearity

4.1 Calibration curves

The calibration curves were generated by diluting D133074 with N6.0 purity grade methane using the MFC dynamic dilution system developed by NPL in A1.2.1. The calibration curves were generated using an NPL-developed program, XLGENLINE, which allows for the calculation of the best-fit low degree polynomial calibration function to a set of (X, Y) measurement data, taking into account the uncertainties associated with the data.

The concentrations plotted on the calibration curves were calculated using blend ratios, and the concentrations chosen are equally spread over the ranges of interest. Table 31 summarises the concentrations generated by diluting D133074 with N6.0 purity grade methane.

A minimum of three repeat runs were collected for each point, and the average value was used when during data processing.

Table 31: Concentrations generated by dynamic dilution of D133074.

Dilution factor	Hydrogen ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	Carbon monoxide ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	Oxygen ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	Nitrogen ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)
1.0	104060.89	962.81	1922.80	94213.25
2.0	52030.44	481.40	961.40	47106.62
3.0	34686.96	320.94	640.93	31404.42
4.0	26015.22	240.70	480.70	23553.31
5.5	18920.16	175.06	349.60	17129.68
40.0	2601.52	24.07*	48.07	2355.33
193.0	539.18	4.99*	9.96*	488.15

* Amount fractions below limit of detection of GC-TCD

For all the following calibration curves below, the black dots indicate the calibration points from the MFC dynamic dilution system, the cyan point indicates the static check standard, and the blue line indicates the calibration curve. Visual inspection of the curves indicates that the TCD response for hydrogen, carbon monoxide, oxygen and nitrogen are linear for the amount fractions reported in Table 31. The calculated correlation coefficients (R^2) above 0.995 suggest that the linear regressions fit the data well.

Figure 13 shows the calibration curve generated for the hydrogen component analysed via TCD. The calibration curve covers from 539.18 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ to 104060.89 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$, with R^2 value of 0.9975, which is deemed acceptable.

Figure 13: Calibration curve of hydrogen component via TCD.

Figure 14 shows the calibration curve generated for the carbon monoxide component which covers concentrations 175.06 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ to 962.81 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$, with R^2 value of 0.9984 which is deemed acceptable.

Figure 14: Calibration curve for carbon monoxide component via TCD.

Figure 15 shows the calibration curve generated for the oxygen component which covers concentrations 48.07 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ to 1922.80 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$, with R^2 value of 0.9967 which is deemed acceptable.

Figure 15: Calibration curve for oxygen component via TCD.

Figure 16 shows the calibration curve generated for the nitrogen component which covers concentrations 488.15 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ to 94213.25 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$, with R^2 value of 0.9995 which is deemed acceptable.

Figure 16: Calibration curve for nitrogen component via TCD.

4.2 Inspection of residuals

The residual peak areas for the calibration curves above were calculated and plotted to inspect for any visible trends. A random distribution of residuals around zero, with no clear trend, confirms linearity and that the regression model is valid over the working range.

Figure 17, Figure 18, Figure 19 and Figure 20 show the plot of residual areas from the hydrogen, carbon monoxide, oxygen and nitrogen linear regression data. The distribution of residual peak areas for all the components are random, thus confirming the linearity and working range.

Figure 17: Plot of residual peak area against amount fraction for hydrogen.

Figure 18: Plot of residual peak area against amount fraction for carbon monoxide.

Figure 19: Plot of residual peak area against amount fraction for oxygen.

Figure 20: Plot of residual peak area against amount fraction for nitrogen.

5. Trueness

The calculated amount fractions of hydrogen, carbon monoxide, oxygen and nitrogen in the check standard (D133080) using the calibration curve was compared to the gravimetric value, according to (Equation 1).

(Equation 1)

$$\Delta_m = |c_m - c_{ref}|$$

Where:

Δ_m = the absolute difference between the mean measured value and the reference value;

c_m = the mean measured value; and

c_{ref} = the gravimetric standard reference value.

The expanded uncertainty of the difference was determined by the quadrature sum of the uncertainties of the reference value and the measurement results according to (Equation 2).

(Equation 2)

$$U_{\Delta} = 2 \sqrt{u_m^2 + u_{ref}^2}$$

Where:

U_{Δ} = the expanded uncertainty of the absolute difference between the mean measured value and the reference value ($k = 2$);

u_m = the uncertainty of the mean measured value ($k = 1$); and

u_{ref} = the uncertainty of the reference value ($k = 1$).

The expanded ($k = 2$) uncertainty corresponds to a confidence interval of 95%.

If the expanded uncertainty of the difference is inferior to the absolute difference between the mean measured value and the reference value, the difference is considered significant (highlighted red).

Table 32 shows the summary of the trueness analysis of the calibration curve as measured against the static reference standard D133080. The calculated amount fraction is an average of 3 repeated measurements.

Table 32: Summary of trueness analysis

D133080	Hydrogen	Carbon monoxide	Oxygen	Nitrogen
Gravimetric standard reference value c_{ref} ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	20160.22	1009.28	406.68	19973.57
Uncertainty of the reference value u_{ref} ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	25.24	0.26	0.43	15.97
Mean measured value c_m ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	21169.96	1010.99	432.86	20406.32
Uncertainty of measured value u_m ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	122.32	0.47	2.14	84.77
Relative difference (%)	5.00	0.17	6.44	2.17
Relative trueness uncertainty U_{Δ} (%)	1.24	0.11	1.07	0.86

The hydrogen, carbon monoxide, oxygen and nitrogen measurement were found to have biases larger than the measurement uncertainty compared to the gravimetric amount fraction, which are highlighted as red in Table 32. The main cause of the biases was due to the insufficient purging of the MFC dynamic dilution system with the check standard. There may have been leftover gas from the previously connected dilution standard, as well as the introduction of ambient air during the changing of cylinder. In the future, the system should be purged thoroughly by allowing the standard to flow for at least 5-10 minutes, with all MFC valves open, to mitigate this issue.

6. Precision

6.1 Repeatability

Measurement precision was split into repeatability and intermediate precision to distinguish the uncertainty contribution linked to the instrument (repeatability) and the uncertainty contribution due to day-to-day effects (intermediate precision).

The repeatability of the measurement method was determined by 3 repeat measurements. An example is provided below based on the check standard (D133080). The repeatability was estimated as the maximum relative standard deviation obtained from the measurements, as shown in Table 33.

Table 33: Repeatability of TCD measuring D133080.

Component	Hydrogen	Carbon monoxide	Oxygen	Nitrogen
Gravimetric standard reference value ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	20160.22	1009.28	406.68	19973.57
RSD (%)	0.58	0.04	0.48	0.41

Repeatability values of 5% and below are considered acceptable.

6.2 Within-lab reproducibility (intermediate precision)

The dynamic system was used to generate calibration curves on four separate dates, and the amount fractions of the bulk components in the check standard were calculated through at least 3 repeats on each day. The average calculated amount fractions and relative standard deviations is presented in Table 34.

Table 34: Summary of within-lab reproducibility analysis for TCD detector.

Component	Hydrogen	Carbon monoxide	Oxygen	Nitrogen
10/09/2024 Average measured amount fraction ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	105841.73	966.14	1929.86	94299.21
11/09/2024 Average measured amount fraction ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	108626.40	964.12	1948.85	98252.43
16/09/2024 Average measured amount fraction ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	108899.62	965.71	2000.13	97310.95
02/10/2024 Average measured amount fraction ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	108797.36	962.97	2000.06	94623.71
Standard deviation ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	1470.69	1.47	35.92	1959.57
Relative standard deviation (%)	1.36	0.15	1.82	2.04

Reproducibility values of 5% and below are considered acceptable. The reproducibility for the four components of interest is below 5%, which indicate that the method is suitable for the measurement of these analytes.

7. Limit of detection and limit of quantification

The limit of quantification (LOQ) is the minimum amount fraction of an analyte which can be confidently determined using an analytical method, whereas the limit of detection (LOD) refers to the minimum amount fraction of an analyte which can be confidently detected. In this case, the LOQs and LODs for each component were calculated using the signal-to-noise (S/N) approach, wherein the signal height of a low amount fraction sample is compared to the instrument baseline. A signal-to-noise ratio of 10:1 is considered acceptable for evaluating the LOQ, and a ratio of 3 is acceptable for evaluating the LOD, as described in (Equation 3).

$$LOQ/LOD = x \left(\frac{S}{N} \right) C \quad \text{(Equation 3)}$$

Where:

x = 3 when determining LOD, 10 when determining LOQ;

S = signal height;

N = noise height; and

C = gravimetric amount fraction of the component.

The results of the LOD and LOQ calculation for the components is presented in Table 35.

Table 35: Summary of LOD and LOQ analysis for each component using TCD.

Component	Hydrogen	Carbon monoxide	Oxygen	Nitrogen
LOD ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	1.74	39.70	19.23	24.70
LOQ ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	5.79	132.33	64.09	82.33

8. Interferences

Figure 21 shows TCD channel 2 which is used for nitrogen and carbon monoxide analysis, whereas Figure 22 shows TCD channel 3 which is used for hydrogen and oxygen analysis. Both figures show the overlaid chromatograms of different amount fractions of hydrogen, carbon monoxide, oxygen, and nitrogen. From visual inspection, the different peak areas for all the components of interest are well resolved from each other, regardless of amount fractions.

Ideally, this study would include testing using a range of biomethane impurities to evaluate any interferences with the peaks of the components of interest, in this case, hydrogen, carbon monoxide, oxygen and nitrogen. However, this was not performed due to time constraints. Future work should address this limitation to ensure that there are no interferences which may skew the results.

Figure 22: TCD Channel 3 for hydrogen (retention time: 1.97 minutes) and oxygen (retention time: 3.37 minutes) analysis.

9. Uncertainty budget

The uncertainty budget for each analytical method was calculated according to (Equation 4).

$$U = k \sqrt{u_r^2 + u_{day}^2 + \Delta_m^2} \quad \text{(Equation 4)}$$

Where:

U = the expanded uncertainty of the analytical method;

k = the coverage factor ($k = 2$ for 95% confidence level);

u_r = the relative uncertainty due to measurement repeatability;

u_{day} = the relative uncertainty due to day-to-day variations (within-lab reproducibility); and

Δ_m = the bias of the analytical method.

The result of the uncertainty budgets for the quantification of bulk composition in methane using GC-TCD is summarised in Table 36.

Table 36: Uncertainty budget.

Component	Hydrogen	Carbon Monoxide	Oxygen	Nitrogen
Repeatability u_r (%)	0.58	0.04	0.48	0.41
Reproducibility u_{day} (%)	1.36	0.15	1.82	2.04
Analytical bias Δ_m (%)	5.00	0.17	6.44	2.17
Expanded uncertainty U (%)	10.43	0.46	13.42	6.01

An expanded uncertainty of 5% and less is considered acceptable for the analysis of hydrogen, carbon monoxide, oxygen, and nitrogen in biomethane. Hence, the uncertainty budget calculated for carbon monoxide is fit for purpose. The large combined uncertainty for the hydrogen, oxygen and nitrogen are mainly due to the large biases calculated (see Section 5, Table 32). Sufficient purging of the system before analysing a standard would drastically improve the analytical bias.

10. Conclusion

The evaluation criteria for the validation of the analytical methods using GC-TCD for the analysis of hydrogen, carbon monoxide, oxygen, and nitrogen in biomethane is summarised in Table 37. The criteria that have met the performance requirements are highlighted in green, whereas the criteria that have not been met are highlighted in red.

Table 37: Summary of performance evaluation criteria for validation of analytical method for quantifying bulk matrix composition in biomethane using GC-TCD.

Criterion	Target value	Hydrogen	Carbon monoxide	Oxygen	Nitrogen
Working range (cmol mol ⁻¹)	H ₂ : 0.01 - 10 CO: 0.1 O ₂ : 0.001 - 1 N ₂ : 0.01 - 10	0.0539 – 10.4061	0.0175 – 0.0963	0.0048- 0.1923	0.0488 – 9.4213
R ² over working range	> 0.995	0.9975	0.9984	0.9967	0.9995
LOD (μmol mol ⁻¹)	-	1.74	39.70	19.23	24.70
LOQ (μmol mol ⁻¹)	H ₂ : < 100 CO: < 1000 O ₂ : < 100 N ₂ : < 100	5.79	132.33	64.09	82.33
Trueness (%)	≤ 5.00	5.00	0.17	6.44	2.17
Repeatability u_r (%)	≤ 5.00	0.58	0.04	0.48	0.41
Reproducibility u_{day} (%)	≤ 5.00	1.36	0.15	1.82	2.04
Expanded uncertainty U (%)	≤ 5.00	10.43	0.46	13.42	6.01

The validation of the method for analysing bulk matrix composition in biomethane was performed according to the performance assessment protocol written in A2.1.4. The method described herein for the analysis of hydrogen, carbon monoxide, oxygen, and nitrogen in biomethane using the TCD detector is therefore valid to the above-described acceptance criteria, except for oxygen. As discussed in Section 9, the expanded uncertainties for hydrogen, oxygen and nitrogen can be drastically improved by sufficient purging of the MFC dynamic dilution system for 5-10 minutes to remove remaining gas from the previous standard as well as ambient air.

REPORT

A.2.2.1: Validation of the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for H₂, N₂, CO and O₂ in methane with GC-TCD using the own static standards produced

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1. Introduction

The BiometCAP project is developing a performance assessment protocol (A2.1.4) for evaluating instruments and methods used for biomethane conformity assessment. Here, this performance assessment protocol was tested and validated using the method based on ISO 6974-6 for the determination of H₂, N₂, CO, O₂, methane in biomethane matrices.

The method is based on gas chromatography with a thermal conductivity and (GC-TCD).

The validation parameters evaluated here were selectivity, limit of detection and quantification, working range and linearity, trueness/bias, and precision. Using these results, the measurement uncertainty was calculated for each component.

2. Materials and methods

For analysis the gas chromatograph with 2x TCD and 2x FID was used (only thermal conductivity detectors was used). Plumbing Diagram in annex 1.

Description of individual TCD channels:

- components analysed on TCD1 include carbon dioxide, argon/oxygen, nitrogen, methane, and carbon monoxide.
- components analysed on TCD2 include hydrogen and helium

The analysis utilized a packed column from Wasson company:

- K1 (P0010-072),
- K2S (P02S0-024),
- K2S (P02S0-084),
- K2S (P02S0-120).

A reference mixture produced by CMI in methane matrix.

3. Validation

General overview

The general procedure for determining the performance characteristics of the instrument is summarised in table 1 Detailed process descriptions are provided in the following sections.

table 1 Overview of performance evaluation process

Step	Phase	Description	Document section reference	
1	Planning	Specify the components required to be measured by the instrument and the measurement range for each over which the instrument shall be evaluated.	hydrogen carbon monoxide nitrogen methane oxygen	
2	Planning	Establish the functional descriptions of the response functions assumed by the instrument for each specified component.	The response should be linear.	
3	Planning	Specify a set of reference gas mixtures (calibration gases) with compositions covering all ranges for all components specified in step 1.	own reference materials	
4	Planning	Establish the composition and uncertainty of the calibration gas mixture(s) to be used for routine calibration of the instrument.	hydrogen	0,99 to 8
			carbon monoxide	0,05 to 0,5
			nitrogen	0,5 to 8
			methane	83 to 96
			oxygen	0,5 to 8
			(all content in 10 ⁻² mol/mol)	

The extent of the performance characteristic validation is summarised in table 2.

table 2 extent of validation

Performance characteristic	Analytical application		
	Component identification	Component detection	Component quantification
Selectivity	x	x	x
Limit of detection		x	
Limit of quantification			x
Working range			x
Trueness			x
Precision			x
Rise time			Not applicable
Memory effect and fall time			Not applicable

Based on previous experiences, for this method, the targeted relative within-laboratory reproducibility, $u(R_w)$, is set at 1,5 % and the targeted relative bias, $u(\text{bias})$, is set at 3%.

Selectivity

Here we used a reference mixture sample containing the components of interest.

The selectivity of the method was investigated by studying its ability to measure the analyte of interest in the sample

The method should be optimized to avoid co-elution of the analyte of interest and the other components present in the sample. With the selected GC parameters for this method and with an TCD detector, the following chromatogram was obtained for a mixture sample (Figure 23).

Figure 23 chromatogram shows that oxygen, nitrogen and methane eluates good separated

Limit of detection and quantification

In this case, the method “replicate measurements of test samples with a suitably low amount fraction of the analyte” was chosen.

The limit of detection and quantification (LOD and LOQ) for hydrogen, carbon monoxide, nitrogen, methane, oxygen was calculated with a Signal-to-Noise (S/N) approach. The S/N ratio is determined by comparing the signals from samples with known low amount of analyte with those of blank samples. LOD and LOQ is the determination of the minimum amount at which the analyte can be confidently detected and quantified. Here, the LOD is determined for S/N = 3 and the LOQ for S/N = 10. The results are presented in Table 3.

The results show that the method is sensitive and can be used to analyse samples with low amount interest components.

table 3 Calculated limits of detection and quantification.

Compounds	Target amount	Noise	Signal	S/N at target amount	LOD	LOQ
	(10 ⁻² mol/mol)	(-)	(-)		(10 ⁻² mol/mol)	(10 ⁻² mol/mol)
					(S/N = 3)	(S/N = 10)
hydrogen	0,990	3	1431,4	477,13	0,006	0,021
oxygen	0,202	3	157,9	52,63	0,012	0,038
nitrogen	0,552	3	402,9	134,30	0,012	0,041
methane	83,158	9	18303,0	2033,67	0,123	0,409
carbon monoxide	0,052	1,5	24,4	16,27	0,010	0,032

Working range and linearity

The linearity was assessed by analysing different amounts of the compounds of interest (10^{-2} mol/mol) for all components.

The results for hydrogen measured in the range 0,99 to $8 \cdot 10^{-2}$ mol/mol are shown in Figure 24. As illustrated in Figure 24, the correlation coefficient for hydrogen measured with GC-TCD/TCD is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 0,99 to $8 \cdot 10^{-2}$ mol/mol.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (Figure 25).

Figure 24 Correlation between the area measured with TCD detector and the known amount of sample in 10^{-2} mol/mol

Figure 25 The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-TCD/TCD plotted against known amount of sample in 10^{-2} mol/mol

The results for carbon monoxide measured in the range 0,05 to $0,5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ mol/mol are shown in Figure 26. As illustrated in Figure 26, the correlation coefficient for hydrogen measured with GC-TCD/TCD is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 0,05 to $0,5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ mol/mol.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (Figure 27).

Figure 26 Correlation between the area measured with TCD detector and the known amount of sample in 10^{-2} mol/mol

Figure 27 The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-TCD/TCD plotted against known amount of sample in 10^{-2} mol/mol

The results for nitrogen measured in the range 0,5 to 8 10⁻² mol/mol are shown in Figure 28. As illustrated in Figure 28, the correlation coefficient for hydrogen measured with GC-TCD/TCD is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 0,5 to 8 10⁻² mol/mol.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (Figure 29).

Figure 28 Correlation between the area measured with TCD detector and the known amount of sample in 10⁻² mol/mol

Figure 29 The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-TCD/TCD plotted against known amount of sample in 10⁻² mol/mol

The results for methane measured in the range 83 to 96 10⁻² mol/mol are shown in Figure 30. As illustrated in Figure 30, the correlation coefficient for hydrogen measured with GC-TCD/TCD is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 83 to 96 10⁻² mol/mol.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (Figure 31).

Figure 30 Correlation between the area measured with TCD detector and the known amount of sample in 10⁻² mol/mol

Figure 31 The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-TCD/TCD plotted against known amount of sample in 10⁻² mol/mol

The results for oxygen measured in the range 0,5 to 8 10⁻² mol/mol are shown in Figure 32. As illustrated in Figure 32, the correlation coefficient for hydrogen measured with GC-TCD/TCD is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 0,99 to 8 10⁻² mol/mol.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (Figure 33).

Figure 32 Correlation between the area measured with TCD detector and the known amount of sample in 10⁻² mol/mol

Figure 33 The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-TCD/TCD plotted against known amount of sample in 10⁻² mol/mol

Trueness, Bias

Since it is not possible to take an infinite number of measurements, trueness cannot be measured. A practical assessment of the trueness can however be made. This assessment is normally expressed evaluation against a reference material.

Compare mean measured value, \bar{x} with the reference value x_{ref} f or the reference material. Calculate bias, b , per cent relative bias, $b(\%)$ or the relative per cent recovery (apparent recovery) $R(\%)$.

$$b = \bar{x} - x_{ref}$$

$$b(\%) = \frac{\bar{x} - x_{ref}}{x_{ref}} \times 100$$

$$R(\%) = \frac{\bar{x}}{x_{ref}} \times 100$$

The differences between the calculated concentrations and the expected concentrations are presented in table 4 -

table 8.

table 4 Bias calculated for hydrogen

Results (10 ⁻² mol/mol)	Reference value (10 ⁻² mol/mol)	Bias	relative BIAS
5,726	5,710	0,016	0,29
5,728	5,710	0,018	0,32
5,730	5,710	0,020	0,35
5,727	5,710	0,017	0,29
5,737	5,710	0,027	0,47
	mean	0,020	0,34

table 5 Bias calculated for oxygen

Results (10 ⁻² mol/mol)	Reference value (10 ⁻² mol/mol)	Bias	relative BIAS
0,467	0,471	-0,004	-0,89
0,469	0,471	-0,002	-0,46
0,464	0,471	-0,007	-1,56
0,466	0,471	-0,005	-1,10
0,465	0,471	-0,006	-1,31
	mean	-0,005	-1,06

table 6 Bias calculated for carbon monoxide

Results (10 ⁻² mol/mol)	Reference value (10 ⁻² mol/mol)	Bias	relative BIAS
0,104	0,104	0,000	0,30
0,104	0,104	0,000	0,12
0,103	0,104	0,000	-0,33
0,106	0,104	0,002	2,33
0,106	0,104	0,003	2,69
	mean	0,001	1,02

table 7 Bias calculated for nitrogen

Results (10 ⁻² mol/mol)	Reference value (10 ⁻² mol/mol)	Bias	relative BIAS
5,056	5,055	0,001	0,01
5,060	5,055	0,005	0,10

5,060	5,055	0,004	0,09
5,081	5,055	0,026	0,51
5,065	5,055	0,010	0,20
	mean	0,009	0,18

table 8 Bias calculated for methane

Results (10 ⁻² mol/mol)	Reference value (10 ⁻² mol/mol)	Bias	relative BIAS
88,703	88,712	-0,009	-0,01
88,709	88,712	-0,003	0,00
88,666	88,712	-0,046	-0,05
88,841	88,712	0,129	0,15
88,712	88,712	0,000	0,00
	mean	0,014	0,02

Precision

Protocol: To evaluate repeatability, measure the analyte(s) of interest within a reference material at various concentrations spread across the working range using the same method. Obtain at least 10 replicate measurements and calculate the standard deviation and relative standard deviation.

Precision was assessed by measuring 10 duplicates of hydrogen, oxygen, carbon monoxide, nitrogen and methane on several days. Standard deviation, as well as relative standard deviation. The results are presented in table 9 to table 13.

table 9 Estimation of the intermediate precision for hydrogen using GC-TCD/TCD

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1	5,715	5,737	0,015	0,191
2	5,734	5,731	0,002	0,025
3	5,715	5,724	0,006	0,077
4	3,939	3,954	0,010	0,179
5	3,957	3,953	0,003	0,051
6	3,954	3,943	0,008	0,136
7	7,964	7,976	0,009	0,076
8	7,978	7,971	0,005	0,044
9	7,991	8,003	0,009	0,076
10	8,003	7,944	0,042	0,371
			mean	0,123

table 10 Estimation of the intermediate precision for oxygen using GC-TCD/TCD

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1	0,204	0,202	0,001	0,359
2	0,205	0,209	0,002	0,848
3	0,202	0,200	0,002	0,687
4	0,486	0,465	0,015	2,180
5	0,463	0,466	0,002	0,367
6	0,479	0,471	0,005	0,777
7	0,499	0,505	0,004	0,549
8	0,750	0,745	0,003	0,329
9	0,749	0,745	0,003	0,241
10	0,747	0,752	0,003	0,328
			mean	0,666

table 11 Estimation of the intermediate precision for carbon monoxide using GC-TCD/TCD

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1	0,056	0,054	0,001	1,174
2	0,052	0,054	0,001	1,831
3	0,052	0,053	0,001	1,016
4	0,050	0,048	0,001	1,413
5	0,099	0,101	0,001	0,653
6	0,104	0,104	0,000	0,041
7	0,102	0,104	0,002	1,193
8	0,099	0,098	0,001	0,819
9	0,097	0,103	0,004	2,588
10	0,100	0,101	0,000	0,323
			mean	1,105

table 12 Estimation of the intermediate precision for nitrogen using GC-TCD/TCD

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1	4,995	5,065	0,050	0,700
2	5,088	5,080	0,006	0,077
3	5,056	5,063	0,005	0,067
4	4,009	3,947	0,044	0,782
5	4,020	4,024	0,003	0,054
6	4,008	4,024	0,011	0,199
7	8,050	7,989	0,043	0,376
8	8,017	8,027	0,007	0,063
9	0,569	0,548	0,014	1,817
10	0,548	0,569	0,015	1,879
			mean	0,601

table 13 Estimation of the intermediate precision for methane using GC-TCD/TCD

Replicates	Meas. 1	Meas. 2	S	CV
1	88,614	88,712	0,069	0,055
2	88,777	88,908	0,093	0,074
3	88,595	88,519	0,053	0,043
4	91,407	91,553	0,103	0,079
5	91,463	91,323	0,099	0,076
6	83,275	83,075	0,141	0,120
7	83,036	83,177	0,099	0,085
8	96,018	95,961	0,041	0,030
9	96,030	95,798	0,164	0,121
10	95,899	95,890	0,007	0,005

mean	0,069
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Measurement uncertainties

The expanded uncertainty (k=2) for compounds was calculated using the following formula:

$$u_a(x_i) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (x_j - x_i)^2}{N \cdot (N-1)}}$$

$$u_b(x_i) = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^m u_{RMj}^2}$$

$$u_c(x_i) = \sqrt{u_a(x_i)^2 + u_b(x_i)^2}$$

$$U_{(x_i)} = k \cdot u_{c(x_i)}$$

Where:

- u_a – uncertainty from measurement
- u_b – uncertainties from reference materials
- u_c - combined standard uncertainty
- U_{xi} - expanded standard uncertainty
- k - expansion coefficient
- u_{RMj} - uncertainty of reference material
- x_i - mole fraction of component i
- N - number of measurements

In general for a GC method for this compounds the measurement uncertainty of 2% or less is considered as acceptable and the method is reliable.

The calculations show that the measurement uncertainty for carbon monoxide is 2,5% which is slightly above the limit for reliable methods

The reference and measured value was compared using the parameter E_n

$$E_n = \frac{y_{lab} - y_{ref}}{\sqrt{U_{lab}^2 + U_{ref}^2}}$$

Where:

- y_{lab} – molar fraction of the component determined in the laboratory (mol/mol),
- y_{ref} – molar fraction of the reference value of the measured component (mol/mol),
- U_{lab} – laboratory measurement uncertainty (mol/mol),
- U_{ref} – uncertainty of the reference value (mol/mol).

table 14 The Uncertainty for hydrogen using GC-TCD/TCD

bottle:	content	U(xi)		content	U(xi)		En
		relative	(10 ⁻² mol/mol)		relative	(10 ⁻² mol/mol)	
685271	5,71	0,16	0,01	5,727	1,58	0,090	0,19
5706852	3,94	0,21	0,01	3,95	1,58	0,062	0,25
579223	8,00	0,08	0,01	7,98	1,58	0,126	0,14
D466344	0,99	1,21	0,01	0,98	1,63	0,016	0,74

table 15 The Uncertainty for oxygen using GC-TCD/TCD

bottle:	content	U(xi)		content	U(xi)		En
		relative	(10 ⁻² mol/mol)		relative	(10 ⁻² mol/mol)	
685271	0,471	0,14	0,001	0,470	1,03	0,005	0,24
5706852	0,505	0,14	0,001	0,502	1,09	0,005	0,46
579223	0,745	0,12	0,001	0,747	0,77	0,006	0,34
D466344	0,202	0,99	0,002	0,204	1,62	0,003	0,44

table 16 The Uncertainty for carbon monoxide using GC-TCD/TCD

bottle:	content	U(xi)		content	U(xi)		En
		relative	(10 ⁻² mol/mol)		relative	(10 ⁻² mol/mol)	
685271	5,06	0,02	0,001	5,062	0,26	0,013	0,50
5706852	4,00	0,02	0,001	3,997	0,49	0,019	0,02
579223	8,00	0,01	0,001	7,992	0,37	0,030	0,14
D466344	0,55	0,54	0,003	0,549	0,79	0,004	0,54

table 17 The Uncertainty for nitrogen using GC-TCD/TCD

bottle:	content	U(xi)		content	U(xi)		En
		relative	(10 ⁻² mol/mol)		relative	(10 ⁻² mol/mol)	
685271	88,712	0,01	0,011	88,682	0,41	0,365	0,08
5706852	91,456	0,01	0,011	91,498	0,41	0,377	0,11
579223	83,158	0,01	0,009	83,160	0,41	0,343	0,01
D466344	95,900	0,08	0,077	95,886	0,41	0,393	0,04

table 18 The Uncertainty for methane using GC-TCD/TCD

bottle:	content	U(xi)		content	U(xi)		En
		relative	(10 ⁻² mol/mol)		relative	(10 ⁻² mol/mol)	
685271,00	0,052	1,45	0,001	0,052	2,50	0,001	0,06
5706852,00	0,104	0,56	0,001	0,105	1,93	0,002	0,66
579223,00	0,101	0,52	0,001	0,099	2,57	0,003	0,58

Conclusion

The validation of the method ISO 6974-6 for interest compounds was performed according to the performance assessment protocol.

The measurement method is therefore reliable, sensitive and found to be fit-for-purpose.

Annex 1 - Plumbing Diagram

Column #	Part # or Column Code
Column 1	10m 2493
Column 2	50 m 2378
Column 3	8' K1
Column 4	10' K2S
Column 5a	8' K1
Column 5b	7' K2S
Column 6	2' K2S
Column 7	2' K2S
Column 8	2' K2S
Column 9	50 m 2343

Color denotes Gas Type (ie. Cyan - Hydrogen)

Valve #	Valve Head Part #
Valve 1	15501
Valve 2	15312
Valve 3	15501
Valve 4	15501
Valve 5a	15301
Valve 5b	15301
Valve 8	only mounting supplied

Voltage/Power Requirements	230 Vac/20 Amps
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